

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MOTIVES FOR COMPANIES TO DEVELOP A SYNERGY STRATEGY

Iakobidze Zviad

*The Doctoral Student of Georgian Technical University
Tbilisi, Georgia*

Abstract

The relevance of the work is that due to economic instability, many companies implement a synergy strategy to stay on the market, it is necessary to understand what strategic goal they pursue and how effectively they go to it. Moreover, the beginning of the 21st century is characterized by strong economic instability, as a result of which we see the mergers of many companies that pursue their individual goal: marketing, speculation, or production. This phenomenon requires a deep scientific study of its understanding, consideration of its main features types, and forms that it can take. Therefore, it is the study of the result and analysis of the very essence of the synergy strategy that is the goal of this work. The stated goal involves solving the following problems: to reveal the essence of the basic concepts and principles of synergy; to reveal the motives for implementing the synergy strategy; to show the forms and types of its manifestation; and to identify the final result of the strategy. The object of study is synergy. The subject is theoretical aspects that reveal the essence of synergy.

Keywords: synergy strategy, strategic goal, economic instability, synergy principle; final strategy result.

Introduction. At the beginning of the 21st century, a new network economy based on advanced communication and information technologies is emerging in post-industrial society development.

The most important features of the new economy are the active use of economic information systems and knowledge management tools, progressive intellectualization of goods and services, the emergence of a single knowledge space, formation of a knowledge market, emergence of a network society based on knowledge, globalization of competition, distribution of risks and resources, formation of new organizations and enterprises as basic socio-economic units.

In the new economy of the 21st century, a significant part of the value created by society is formed thanks to knowledge objectified in products and services, which are the result of the synergy strategy. The synergy strategy is for obtaining competitive advantages by combining two or more business units (business units) in one hand. The development of the modern market is associated with a constant increase in the degree of intelligence of the offered goods and services. Therefore, it is always necessary to increase your competitive level in time, so as not to leave the market.

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Discussion.

Synergism is a strategic advantage that occurs when two or more enterprises are united in one set of hands; efficiency increases, which is manifested in increased productivity and/or reduced production costs.

However, O. Yermansky in his work "The Theory and Practice of Rationalization," published in 1925, substantiated the principle of synergism through an arithmetic formula, which states: that the organizational sum is greater than the arithmetic sum of the forces of its components:

$$\sum(\mathbf{a, b, c, \dots, n}) + \mathbf{a + b + c + \dots + n.}$$

This term (synergism) was not encountered in business literature at that time, but it still implied some force that gave an additional effect from the combination of some organizational components.

Although the concept of synergism appeared quite recently, the signs of this effect were formulated long ago: two principles of Being and five principles of Formation.

- Homeostaticity. Homeostasis is the maintenance of the system's functioning program within certain limits that allow it to pursue its goal.
- Hierarchy. The main meaning of structural hierarchy is the composite nature of higher levels to lower ones.

What is structure-order for a lower level is a structureless element of chaos, a building material, for a higher level. The described nature of the order parameters is called the principle of subordination when a

change in the order parameter seems to synchronously conduct the behavior of many lower-level elements that form the system, and the phenomenon of their coherent, i.e. mutually agreed upon, coexistence is sometimes called the phenomenon of self-organization.

The five principles of Formation characterize the phase of transformation, renewal of the system, its successive passage through the death of the old order, the chaos of testing alternatives, and, finally, the birth of a new order.

- **Nonlinearity.** Nonlinearity is a violation of the superposition principle in a certain phenomenon: the result of the sum of influences on the system is not equal to the sum of the results of these influences. The results of the acting causes cannot be added up. In a more humanitarian, qualitative sense: the result is disproportionate to the efforts. In crises, which are common in our time, nonlinear methods are in demand.

- **Non-closure (openness).** Impossibility of neglecting the interaction of the system with its environment. In the language of hierarchical levels, the principle of openness emphasizes two important circumstances. Firstly, this is the possibility of self-organization of being in the form of the existence of stable nonequilibrium structures at the macro level (openness of the macro level to the micro level with fixed control parameters). Secondly, the possibility of self-organization of formation, i.e. the possibility of changing the type of nonequilibrium structure. It turns out that when moving from one homeostasis position to another, in the area of strong nonlinearity, the system necessarily becomes open at points of instability.

- **Instability.** Contains the two previous ones, and, in general, for a long time was considered a defect, a shortcoming of the system. Well, who will design an unstable bicycle or airplane? This was the case until recently, when a new generation of robots was needed, reconfigurable from one homeostasis program to another; learning systems capable of perceiving different behavior models. Here, each time, the system approaches a choice point (a bifurcation point).

The significance of bifurcation points is also in the fact that only at them can one influence the choice of the system's behavior, its fate, not by force, but by information, i.e. by arbitrarily weak influences.

It is the property of instability at critical moments in the development of systems that allows us to understand the "role of personality in history", allows us to expand the state spaces of systems, and generate information in a mixed chaotic layer.

- **Dynamic hierarchy (emergence).** This is a generalization of the principle of subordination to the processes of formation, when it is necessary to consider the interaction of more than two levels, and the process of formation itself is a process of disappearance, and then the birth of one of them in the process of interaction of at least three hierarchical levels of the system. This is the main principle of the system's passage through bifurcation points, its formation, birth, and death of hierarchical levels.

- **Observability.** The principle of observability emphasizes the limitations and relativity of our ideas about the system in the final experiment. In synergetics,

this is the relativity of interpretations to the scale of observations and the original expected result. On the one hand, what was chaos from the standpoint of the macro level turns into a structure when moving to the scale of the micro level. That is, the very concepts of order and chaos, Being and Formation are relative to the window of observation. The principle of observability is understood as an open complex principle; its inclusion makes the system of principles of synergetics open to replenishment with philosophical-methodological and systemic interpretations.

Tali also formulated other principles based on the concepts of synergism: 1) "the principle of positive selection of force" - such a combination of forces (workers, means of production, etc.), when they reinforce, complement one another; for this, it is necessary to know the properties of these selected forces; 2) "the law of accumulation of training opportunities", which allows having a constant expenditure of forces to get a greater result; the condition for the accumulation of exercises (skills) is the repetition of the same actions, movements.

The concept of I. Ansoff on synergism has proven itself as the most stable (1960) - this author is mainly associated with the substantiation of the concept of the synergistic effect ("Synergism and Resources", work "Corporate Strategy", 1965). I. Ansoff says that this effect, "the capable level of production of an integrated company, exceeding the value of similar indicators of its functioning in separate divisions, is often denoted by the equations $2 + 2 = 5$ ". He suggests calling it synergism. Comparison of the mathematical expression of O.A. Ermansky, its explanation, and the formative record of synergy and disclosure of its meaning - " $2 + 2 = 5$ " the general meaning is clear. Although one speaks of a reasonable organization, the other - of corporate efficiency.

Synergy strategy is the acquisition of a strategy of competitive advantages by combining two or more business units (business units) in one hand.

The presence of a synergy effect and the ability to manage this effect creates a specific competitive advantage, which is realized at the level of the enterprise as a whole and which, ultimately, manifests itself in different commodity markets in a reduced level of costs or the production of unique properties.

Synergy strategy leads to an increase in the efficiency of activities due to the joint use of resources (synergy of technologies and costs), market employment (joint sales), or scope of activity (synergy of planning and management). The importance of the synergy strategy is thus that it helps to achieve higher production profitability when business units are interconnected than when they are managed separately.

American economists W. King and D. Cleland consider synergy to be an important factor in the selection, development, and detailing of strategies. They note that the synergy effect, no matter how large it is, will not appear on its own; it must be planned and visible. This is possible if the synergy is identified, defined, and included in reasonable plans.

The synergy effect is most clearly manifested at the level of the portfolio (corporate) strategy, no matter

how possible and within one business unit. Business practice shows that the effect of joint activities is always higher than the minimum independent trend due to the possibility of cooperation and interconnection.

However, the synergy effect is an extremely complex phenomenon; its achievement depends on the beneficial combination of many different elements. The omission of at least one of these elements or their parts can lead to the achievement of such a result.

To avoid this, it is advisable to start a collective discussion of these specialists with knowledge in the areas under consideration. This allows you to change your thinking at the level of desires and expectations, so often inherent in the strategies of searching for a synergistic effect.

In addition, the management of the enterprise must be organized in such a way that the achievement of security guarantees synergy on the part of the managers of business units. Otherwise, a negative synergy effect occurs, which means " $2 + 2 < 4$ ".

A synergistic portfolio is a group of entrepreneurs who have one owner and adhere to a policy of relations with each other. Its opposite is a differentiated portfolio or a conglomerate. An example of a synergistic portfolio can be an airline providing hotels, overground transportation, and airport services.

Types of synergy, according to the consideration of these concepts, and directions from many sources, explain their occurrence in different ways; in one case he discovered a changing situation, in another - it is necessary to make significant efforts to obtain this effect. It should be borne in mind that in the issue of synergy, there are many small, sometimes contradictory. In this regard, there are different interpretations of the types of synergy. Here is one of them:

- **Market synergy.** It is provided in such a way as joint sale of products of one group. It can be obtained with the help of a product strategy or joint development

in the market. Market synergistic elements are well-recommended brands and firms when labeling new products. Examples of brands: Fa, Camey

- **Cost synergy.** This is the general use of equipment, distribution network, and sales personnel. For example Mercedes, Chrysler

- **Technological synergy.** This is possible when transferring technologies developed for one purpose, i.e. a sphere. Often this effect gives impetus to the creation of know-how. For example: Teflon was created by DuPont to facilitate the return of ships.

- **Managerial synergy.** It is known that good top-level managers lack the means, the means for train and improve the skills of top-level managers, this means that an attempt to obtain a synergistic effect from the use of gifted top-level managers by merging and acquiring enterprises often has serious grounds.

However, I. Ansoff identifies the following types of synergy:

- **Trade.** It is understood that the general directions of distribution, existence in an integrated system, advertising, marketing, and reputation allow to achieve an increase in profit with fixed investments;

- **Operational.** There is a use of higher production capacities, an effect of scale is achieved;

- **Managerial.** In many ways, they determine the overall positive effect of science: the unification of skills, and the expansion of the intellectual knowledge bases of the integrated organization.

- **Joint.** In the case of joint understandings, there is the presence of all traditional types of synergy effect mentioned above. The presence of at least two typology features gives us the right to consider the effect joint. Moreover, it is worth considering that the larger the company, the more opportunities it has to apply synergy and the more opportunities it has to increase its effect. Possible forms of manifestation of systematized synergy in large groups are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Forms of manifestation of the synergy effect		
Revenue growth	Cost reduction	Combined action
Expansion of the range of services provided	Operational savings (cost reduction due to reduction of fixed costs)	Functional synergy (the target firm is stronger in areas where the acquiring firm is weak)
Increase in market share, accumulation of critical mass for participation in large projects	Increased efficiency of work with suppliers	Stabilization of cash flows by combining companies with different life cycles
	Financial savings	Improvement of corporate culture, strategy
	Elimination of duplicate functions	

The final result of the strategy implementation will affect the key moments of business introduction. Let's consider them in Figure 1.

Conclusion. In this paper, a detailed analysis of synergy as a phenomenon and as a subject of strategy was conducted. A striking example of synergy strategy in gas companies was also analyzed.

The negative principle of this strategy is its instability, so this strategy must be carefully thought out for all its key factors because its nonlinearity will either bring you a double positive effect or a negative one.

The motives for implementing this strategy may be the following. Marketing - by increasing market share and differentiating the volume of goods or services, the company will be able to significantly increase the amount of revenue. Speculative - by dividing capital, the company will be able to receive state benefits for profit, reduce costs, and obtain the right to choose the depreciation rate itself. Investment - more typical for highly capital-intensive companies whose investments take a long time to pay off, helps the company to quickly adapt to changes in the economy and promotes new know-how. Production - helps companies stay afloat with mutual benefit, has a combined effect when one company, during a merger, helps another in its weak areas of activity.

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